

Amelogenesis: Nature's 3D printing system for multi-scale laminates

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The best designs: simple or complex?

KISS
(keep it simple, stupid!)

K. Johnson
Lockheed Skunk Works
~1960

rely on simplest possible stress analysis problem

- use materials in such a way that they are linear
- failure predicted by a small number of tests

vs.

very complex stress analysis problem

- design exploits complexity
- works best in nonlinear regime

How many damage tests do you need?

To get a working bone:

e.g., vertebrates:

alive now: $10^{11} - 10^{15}$

DNA base pairs: 10^9

mutation rate: 10^{-9} (per base pair per generation)

generations: 10^9

total number of tests:* $10^{20} - 10^{24}$

* not counting “epigenetic” phenomena
(heritable changes in gene expression)

<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/vertebrate>

<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Genome>

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Mutation_rate

typical aerospace problems

To certify an airframe material

10^4 coupon tests

plus a few tests of subcomponents, components, and entire structures

(A. Fawcett, J. Trostle, S. Ward, 1997)

To optimize a wing

Age, N., E. Andreassen, B.S. Lazarov, and O. Sigmund, 2017, Nature, 550(7674): pp. 84.

- very large number of computational degrees of freedom
- constrained optimization (gradient method)
- finite element computation (elasticity)
- typically $\sim 10^2 - 10^3$ iterations (design “tests”)

it's a convex problem

perpetually adaptive design

continuous lifetime re-modeling:

- 10^{10} osteocytes sense nonlinearity (microcracks)
- osteocyte recruits osteoclasts and osteoblasts
- osteoclasts remove bone and osteoblasts remake it
- 7% of bone remodeled every year
- osteocyte network also helps govern body chemistry

similar to number of neurons in the brain

Buenzli, P.R. and N.A. Sims, 2015, "Quantifying the osteocyte network in the human skeleton", *Bone*, 75: pp. 144-150

Dental enamel: very hard tissue formed by ameloblast cells

- Ameloblasts create enamel as the outer layer of a tooth
- Enamel microstructure is optimized for strength and toughness

Nature invents 3D printing!

M. Mouse *et al.*, "3D Printing" US Patent No. zero, 200,000,000 B.C.*
*late Triassic period for mammalian teeth, e.g., P.D. Gingerich, *Patterns of Evolution in the Mammalian Fossil Record*, in *Patterns of Evolution*, ed. A. Hallam, Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1977

Rat ameloblasts making layered enamel

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The laminated-composite microstructure of rodent incisor enamel

tooth erupts throughout the life of the animal (it's a rodent)

cleavage fracture results in a very sharp tip (several microns)

the white layer is hard enamel

all photographs courtesy of Shane White, UCLA

What controls the dynamic positioning of the cells as they print enamel microstructure?

- There is **no external governing machinery** that pushes cells around according to a “design blueprint”
- **Each cell must read it’s own instantaneous context** and decide what to do, and when to do it, based solely on that context
- The **prevalent paradigm** (since Alan Turing, 1952) assumes that the “context” is built out of **spatial gradients in chemical factors**
- We now demonstrate that **the evolving local strain field around an individual cell contains all the information that the cell needs**

Cells as strain-cued automata

Evolving strain fields offer much timing and positional information

Single cell response function:

displacement of cell membrane → a strain-cued response

e.g., cell moves to restore a preferred cell density

e.g., cell transforms to another state

No stress field is calculated!

Occam's razor: why include what we don't need?

strain field only → complete and predictive formulation

$$\frac{d(\text{elastic energy density})/dt}{\text{metabolic power}} \approx 10^{-6} - 10^{-5}$$

→ a stress field is unlikely to sustain timing and positional information accurately for sufficiently long times.

why ameloblasts see transition to secretory stage as a strain transformation

Wave equation with a transformation front

Tendency to restore a preferred density ρ_0 :

$$\varepsilon_x = \frac{\partial u}{\partial x}$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} = -k \frac{1}{(1 + \varepsilon_x)^m} \frac{\partial \varepsilon_x}{\partial x} \quad \leftarrow \text{nonlinear restorative law}$$

transform gradually to slope α when: $|\varepsilon_x| > \varepsilon_c \quad \leftarrow \text{strain trigger}$

$$\Delta\phi = 1 - \cos\alpha$$

$$\phi = 1 + \Delta\phi \cdot f(X)$$

complete wave equation:

$$\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} = k_a \frac{\phi}{(1 + \partial u / \partial x)^2} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} - k_a \frac{1}{1 + \partial u / \partial x} \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x}$$

nonzero only within front

The strain transformation induces a traveling pulse of strain

The strain transformation induces a traveling pulse of strain

Scott Russell's "Wave of Translation" (1845)

"I was observing the motion of a boat which was rapidly drawn along a narrow channel by a pair of horses, when the boat suddenly stopped—not so the mass of water in the channel which it had put in motion; it ... rolled forward with great velocity, assuming the form of a large solitary elevation, a rounded, smooth and well-defined heap of water

solitary wave
in a
laboratory

" ... I followed it on horseback, and overtook it still rolling on at a rate of some **eight or nine miles an hour.**"

$$\text{velocity of pulse in human molar} = 120 \mu\text{m/day} \approx \frac{8-9 \text{ miles/hour}}{10^9}$$

Next question: how is the cross-plied laminate formed?

ameloblasts print a cross-plied laminated structure in the mouse incisor

two layers visible in this light micrograph

Kinematic feedback for shear displacements

The shear enhancement rule:
$$\bar{S}_i = \sum_j \left\{ \frac{d_{ij} - d}{d} \hat{r}_{ij} + S_{ij}^{(\text{shear})} \right\}$$

where
$$S_{ij}^{(\text{shear})} = c_1 V \exp[-c_2 V^2]$$

with
$$V = \left| \mathbf{v}_{ij}^{(\text{shear})} \right|$$
 shear velocity between two cells

i.e., when cells sense sliding, they accentuate it

- The cells move individually in response to their local strain environment
- The rules are isotropic: no bias exists
- The growth front is curved

Spontaneous formation of sliding layers

Next question: why do layers tilt forward?

Cells that secrete later pursue cells that secreted earlier in the downstream direction to restore preferred cell density

cross-sectional plane

Last question: how do cells form bands (thicker laminae)?

“cohorts” or “gangs” of cells form laminae of differently oriented fibers

Courtesy Van Thompson, NYU

Coupled solitary waves: dual transformations

“strain” transformation
 cells begin to secrete –
 geometry changes

strain field within the dual-transformation front cycles as the system propagates

It pulsates!

“segmentation”

pulsating pair of solitary waves breaks initially uniform symmetry of population into periodic segments

Nature embraces complexity:
all the above can only happen in a strongly nonlinear system

Summary - I

Cells acting in response to strain cues can create the microstructural patterns of tough, strong dental enamel

- *solitary waves form very stable timing signal*
- *shear feedback nucleates cross-plyed laminate structures*
- *maintenance of cell number density creates forward tilt to laminae*
- *cyclic dual transformations (motility and strain) pattern cells in segments, which can be the templates for thicker laminae*

Ameloblasts do all this:

- *using internally generated power to move, rather than relying on externally imposed energy gradients, and*
- *using built-in response functions, rather than needing to be orchestrated by a central controller*

Summary - II

Optimized mechanical properties of dental enamel depend on the geometry of the microstructure

That microstructural geometry can be formed entirely by cells that sense strains, i.e., how their local environment evolves as the entire cell population reacts to the changing geometry of the developing organ

The theory has remarkably few parameters, all of which relate directly to geometry

Occam's razor: it is difficult to conceive of a theory that connects organ geometry to cell actions that is simpler than a strain-cue theory